

USG (4-14%). Labeled N utilization was 42% with PU, 30% in grain and 12% in straw (see figure). Only 8% of the labeled N applied as USG was utilized (6% in grain and 2% in straw).

Isotopic composition of rice grain and straw showed that 40% grain N and 35%

straw N were derived from PU; 13% grain N and 12% straw N were derived from USG.

Soil analysis at harvest showed that 26% of the labeled N from PU and 13% from USG were retained in the soil. Total recovery of labeled N in crop and

soil was 68% for PU, 21% for USG; 32% PU N and 79% USG N was not accounted for in the N balance. The large deficit of N from USG was attributed to its rapid movement and leaching from concentrated zones at placement sites. □

Sesbania rostrata — a lower-cost source of N for rice

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We studied the effect of stem-root nodulating *S. rostrata* and sunn hemp *Crotalaria jancea* on transplanted irrigated rice Mandya Vijaya (145-150 d duration) during summer 1988.

Soil of the experimental site was red sandy loam (Alfisols), pH 6.3, medium N (1.1% organic matter), 10.6 kg available Olsen's P/ha, and 151 kg available K/ha. N content was 4.1% in *S. rostrata* and 3.2% in sunn hemp.

At the same level of applied N, yield increased significantly (15%) over farmers' practice (treatment 1), with 30% N supplied through *S. rostrata* (treatment 2) (see table). The cost

involved in supplying N through *S. rostrata* was \$12, compared to urea cost of \$15. Use of *S. rostrata* increased net profit by \$125/ha. *S. rostrata* (treatment 4) could substitute for fertilizer N up to 70 kg N/ha (treatment 6) without significant yield reduction.

S. rostrata was significantly superior to sunn hemp (treatment 5). Uptake of N was better with *S. rostrata*. □

Effect of *S. rostrata* on rice yield. ^a Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total uptake of N in grain + straw (kg/ha)
1. 100 kg N/ha as urea in 3 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 panicle initiation (farmers' practice)	4.5	92
2. 30 kg N/ha through <i>S. rostrata</i> + 70 kg N/ha as urea in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	5.2	110
3. 30 kg N/ha through sunn hemp <i>C. jancea</i> + 70 kg N/ha in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	4.8	97
4. <i>S. rostrata</i> to supply 70 kg N/ha	3.4	76
5. Sunn hemp to supply 70 kg N/ha	3.0	68
6. 70 kg N/ha as urea in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	3.2	71
7. Control (no N)	2.4	47
LSD (0.05)	0.3	6
CV (%)	10.8	5.3

^aAll treatments received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha.

Nitrogen-use efficiency with hand- and machine-applied N fertilizers in wetland rice soils

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Prilled urea (PU) farmer's split (F), researcher's split (R), modified split (M), applicator placed (AP); and urea

supergranules (USG) hand placed (H) and AP were compared in a field experiment during the 1986 dry season. BR3 was the test variety.

Soil was clay loam (Paleudults) with pH 6.5, 1.05% organic matter, CEC 24 meq/100 g, 0.07% total N, and incubated 57 ppm NH₄⁺-N (incubated at 30 °C for 1 wk). Two rates of N (58 and 87 kg/ha) and 1 control treatment were used. P at 17.6 kg/ha, K at 33.2 kg/ha, and S at 20 kg/ha were applied

Effect of N fertilizer application method on yield of BR3 and agronomic efficiency of N, 1986 dry season, BRRI, Joydebpur, Bangladesh. ^a

Treatment ^a	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Agronomic efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
Control	86	210 e	195 c	3.6 c	-
58 PU (F)	93	243 d	231 b	4.9 ab	23
58 PU (R)	91	286 bc	269 ab	4.6 b	18
58 PU (M)	89	267 bcd	256 ab	4.8 ab	20
58 PU (AP)	94	309 a	295 a	5.3 a	30
58 USG (H)	93	299 a	283 a	5.3 ab	29
58 USG (AP)	94	285 abc	269 ab	5.4 a	31
87 PU (F)	91	272 abcd	263 ab	5.2 ab	19
87 PU (R)	92	260 cd	242 b	5.0 ab	16
87 PU (M)	94	281 abcd	268 ab	4.9 ab	15
87 USG (H)	94	293 ab	271 ab	5.4 a	20
CV (%)	4	2	2	8	

^a Within a column, means followed by a common letter do not vary significantly at the 5% level of DMRT. ^b F = 1/3 basal + 1/3 30 d after transplanting (DT) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI), R = 2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI, M = 1/3 15 DT + 30 DT + 1/3 at PI, AP = applicator-placed at 10-12 cm depth, H = hand-placed at about 10-12 cm depth.